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Research Article

**“KNOWLEDGE OF MEDICAL FACULTY
TOWARDS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: A STUDY OF MEDICAL
COLLEGES IN LAHORE”**Dr. Shehir Bano¹, Dr. Samiya Nazir¹, Dr. Sara Aslam¹¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

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Abstract:

Introduction: This research is objected to explore about current practices of inclusive education in Pakistan. In every society medical students are soundless but noticeable participants. In accordance with country policies and implementations, medical students face many barriers to getting education. It is having much importance to craft such study environment that meets the requirements of medical students also.

Methodology: A descriptive investigation design was employed for this education in order to investigate regular medical teacher knowledge concerning inclusive medical education practices in the medical college in Lahore setting. Data from the participants was gathered in one point in time. The selected population for this study is government medical college of Lahore, Punjab. The population of medical college from respected area has been drawn from data of University of Health Sciences Lahore. From University of Health Sciences Lahore data bank total population of medical colleges 6 medical college. By applying simple random sampling, 10 samples of 10 medical teachers in each sample has been taken. The sample size for this study has been objected as 100 medical teachers out of total population.

Results: SPSS regression analysis of 100 recorded responses have been run and the results of test showed that there is 90 percent change effect of independent variable on dependent variable. The significance level has been reported as .000 highly significant of study variables in this study. In regression analysis 't' value is significantly higher than 2 with F value 292.82 showing the results of model fit. This association of independent variable 'medical teacher's knowledge' and dependent variable 'Inclusive medical education' representing by recorded responses are highly associated in Pakistani perspective of this study.

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INTRODUCTION:

This research is objected to explore about current practices of inclusive education in Pakistan. In every society medical students are soundless but noticeable participants. In accordance with country policies and implementations, medical students face many barriers to getting education. It is having much importance to craft such study environment that meets the requirements of medical students also. It has been thought by scholars that the inn regular college system inclusion is best way to handle the educational needs for all medical students. In this way society and tutors must change their selves for inclusive practices. This research will explore the effectiveness of inclusive education in Pakistan as well it will be noticed 6 how for medical teacher's knowledge for inclusive education are important for medical students in inclusive education. Microteaching being a powerful tool for teaching methodology is an underutilized tool in this institution. Henceforth, the present study was conducted among the medical teachers to evaluate their knowledge and attitude towards microteaching and also to add some light on the changing form of medical education.

Research Objectives:

- To assess the association of medical teachers' knowledge about inclusive education
- To analyze the medical teachers training as a mediator between knowledge and inclusive education

METHODOLOGY:

A descriptive investigation design was employed for this education in order to investigate regular medical teacher knowledge concerning inclusive medical education practices in the medical college in Lahore setting. Data from the participants was gathered in one point in time. The selected population for this study is government medical college of Lahore, Punjab. The population of medical college from respected area has

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The five-point Likert scale rating response is used for the quantitative analysis in SPSS. The survey had three main sections. Section one describes the personal information of medical teachers' demographic variables such as gender, education, training about inclusive education and their experience of teaching in the inclusive arrangement. Section two of this scale comprises of twelve questions regarding inclusive medical education in Pakistan, this section contains the inclusive related questions for trying to know about their perceived motive for inclusion. Section three also contains twelve questions regarding medical teachers' knowledge towards inclusive education in Pakistan. This scale is used to find out teachers' response for having sufficient knowledge regarding awareness about inclusion implementations and how to treat the medical students in classrooms.

RESULTS:

SPSS regression analysis of 100 recorded responses have been run and the results of test showed that there is 90 percent change effect of independent variable on dependent variable. The significance level has been reported as .000 highly significant of study variables in this study. In regression analysis 't' value is significantly higher than 2 with F value 292.82 showing the results of model fit. This association of independent variable 'medical teacher's knowledge' and dependent variable 'Inclusive medical education' representing by recorded responses are highly associated in Pakistani perspective of this study.

Table 1: Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.877	22

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

		Teacher Knowledge	Teacher Attitude
Teacher Medical Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.77**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3: Bivariate Liner Regression

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	101.54	1.3	101.89	25.516	.000 ^b
	Residual	65.41	277.7	.199		
	Total	166.95	279			

a. Dependent Variable: Medical Teacher Knowledge

b. Predictors: (Constant), Medical Teacher Attitude

Table 4: Mediation

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig.F Change
1	.775	.74	.74	.391	.679	984.11	1	277	.000
2	.775	.74	.74	.391	.001	.7314	1	276	.377

H2: Medical Teacher training plays as mediating role between medical teachers attitude and knowledge of teachers regarding inclusive medical education

Looking at Model summary, the R Square Change value shows that teacher attitude accounts for 78.4 per cent in medical teacher knowledge and is significant at $p=.000$, whereas training accounts for only 1 percent in medical teacher knowledge and is not statistically significant ($p=.392$) which leads this hypothetical effect as not verified.

DISCUSSION:

Medical teacher's knowledge is having prominent significant in order to regulate the educational activities in medical colleges effectively, In this study the prime focus is to target medical teacher knowledge for successful implementation of inclusive education in Pakistan. Hodkinson (2005) believes that the knowledge of medical teacher is heavily necessary for the proper effectiveness of inclusion medical educational program in any country. In India study has been established by Singal (2008) by targeting the inclusive medical education system at the different levels of medical institutions through statistical technique. She reported that the preceding behavior and expertise of the teacher is having the significant impact on the inclusive implementation program in India. Furthermore it has been assessed in this study that what are the ground realities of inclusive educational classrooms and practices that re being carried out for regular classrooms including the medical students with difficulties. She enclosed that the knowledge of teachers and beliefs about inclusive. In the research organized by Sadler (2005) found that 88% teachers in the inclusive program responded to have limited or very less knowledge of inclusion no one of the participant in inclusive study responded as having excessive or satisfactory knowledge regarding inclusive educational program. Same adverse result has been reported by Gaad and Khan (2007) for teachers to be out of knowledge for inclusive educational practices. Responding teachers accepted that they have very limited information. It is there for concluded that teacher's less or limited knowledge is the significant barrier for the effective implementation of inclusive education.

Teacher's knowledge for inclusive teaching is always being the main issue against the proper implementation program. Most of the teachers explained that policies regarding inclusive are being imposed and implemented so that they are not having interest in it (Ali, Mustapha & Jelas, 2006). On the next aspect, teachers are not having the inclusive background for teaching medical students with difficulties, In the presence of unspecialized teachers with maximum experience to teach in inclusive education environment may not have the healthy effect on teaching standards of inclusive setting (Meng, 2008).

CONCLUSION:

In this study it has been evaluated that most of the teachers in medical colleges have shown knowledge towards inclusive educational implementations in Pakistan, The lesser frequency of teacher has also

responded as lesser knowledge. The knowledge and inclusive implementations have analysed as having significant association, teacher's knowledge has witnessed as strong change in implementations of inclusive education in medical colleges in Lahore. In this study by assessing the demographic elements of teachers, it has been observed that 60 percent of medical teachers have not received any training regarding inclusive education. This needs to policy implementations for holding training of teachers for assisting them towards positive and healthy approaches in inclusive practices at colleges

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